

AIDV-WG Shared Citation Library

Supporting Output

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Abstract: The AIDV-WG Shared Citation Library on the zotero platform available at <https://www.zotero.org/groups/4922635/aidv-wg/library> was developed to support working group members' research and particularly to support these three concurrent AIDV-WG outputs: *Bill of Rights Recommendation*[\[i\]](#), *Guidance on Informed Consent*[\[ii\]](#), and the *Guidance for Ethics Committees Reviewing AI and Data Visitation*[\[iii\]](#).

The AIDV WG's open, shared citation library explores emerging Jurisdictional and Special Interest AI Rights and Protections for AI/LLM/Model creators, deployers, and harmed/ impacted parties at the International, Regional, National, and Municipal levels and within disciplinary and niche scenarios with an emphasis on policies that intersect human rights, education, ethics, health/medicine, regulation/governance and risk.

We have categorized these resources by whether they relate to the categories of: "Disciplinary or Special Interest Rights and Protections", Education, Ethics, "Healthcare and Medicine", "Generative AI Publishing/Authorship and Copyright", "Informed Consent", "Jurisdictional Rights Declarations and Acts", Legal, "Privacy and Surveillance", Risks, and "Related News Stories". The assets in our shared library are tagged by country and jurisdiction where relevant.

Impact: The AIDV-WG's shared citation library's purpose is to ease effort toward citation management for AIDV-WG members and others researching and writing on AI policy topics.

Contribution to United Nations SDGs: The AIDV-WG Shared Citation Library contains content related to several indicated SDGs and includes 44 SDG specific citations as of August 20, 2024.

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RDA webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/activity/>

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EOSC-Future & RDA Artificial Intelligence/Data Visitation Workgroup

Shared Citation Library

Version 1.0 AUGUST 19, 2024

Contributor(s): AIDV Working Group
Maintained by Natalie Meyers (US)

Shared Citation Library

zotero.org/groups/4922635/aidv-wg/library

Tagged by:

- Country
- AIDV SubTeam
- Keyword

Categorized by:

- Jurisdictional Rights Declarations & Acts
- Disciplinary & Special Interest Rights & Protections
- Education
- Ethics
- Generative AI/Publishing, Authorship, Copyright
- Healthcare/Medicine
- Informed Consent
- Legal
- Privacy/Surveillance
- Related News Stories
- Risk

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The AIDV WG's open, shared citation library,¹¹ explores emerging Jurisdictional and Special Interest AI Rights and Protections for AI/LLM/Model creators, deployers, and harmed/ impacted

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ⁱ RDA AIDV WG. Eyiuche Ezigbo^{ID}(NG), Shiny Martis B^{ID}(FR), Natalie Meyers^{ID}(US), Ronit Purian-Lukatch^{ID}(IL), Yeyang Su^{ID}(CN) (August 20, 2024) AI Bill of Rights Recommendation. doi: 10.15497/RDA00124

ⁱⁱ RDA AIDV WG, Cambon-Thomsen A, Chassang G, Hackett K, Retanan LJ, Dubruel N (July 23, 2024) Guidance on Informed Consent in Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation. Research Data Alliance. doi: 10.15497/RDA00121 https://www.rd-alliance.org/group_output/guidance-for-informed-consent-in-the-context-of-artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation/

ⁱⁱⁱ RDA AIDV WG, (Aug 15 2024). Guidance for Ethics Committees Reviewing AI and Data Visitation. Research Data Alliance. doi: 10.15497/RDA00122 https://www.rd-alliance.org/group_output/guidance-for-informed-consent-in-the-context-of-artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation/